

UNIQUENESS AND ARTISTIC STYLE OF ABDULLA ORIPOV'S CREATION

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ABSTRACT

This article reveals the artistic interpretation of Abdulla Oripov's work, the unique style of his poetry, his high talent and the peculiarities of his poems.

The work of the people's poet of Uzbekistan Abdulla Oripov is a unique world. The poet's poems are distinguished by sincerity, simple and free language, and an extremely subtle artistic image. In addition, the work of Abdulla Oripov is rich in various themes, such as the Motherland, respect for our great ancestors, the fate of the nation, love and loyalty, in which the poet artistically interprets his emotional experiences at the level of artistic discovery. At the same time, in each poem of the poet, the national spirit and unique tones are clearly felt [1].

Indeed, this country loves its poet son very much. He reads and memorizes his poems. We saw in the fields how the collective farmers read Abdullah's poems at lunchtime, and the nursing women listened with joyful imagination. We heard that the old people who listened to his poems applauded, saying: "Live long, my son." Going on long journeys, we saw only drivers who took Abdulla Oripov's poems with them, and builders who held his poems in their hands.

Abdulla Oripov is very cleverly and artistically uses proverbs, proverbs and expressions created by our wise people, as a result of which the proverbs mentioned by the poet begin their poetic life anew. In particular, the poet effectively used folk proverbs in his quatrains. In his quatrains "Philosophy that I understood", "Listen, this will sound forever", "They say the dog barks, the caravan goes", "The nightingale is like an owl among the flock". The poet did not quote these proverbs just to prove his opinion, but enriched these proverbs with new facets and special interpretations, which is his innovation [2].

This world is like a market.

It's like a market, and it makes sense.

I didn't even see the two of them

One who says I'm bad [3].

To these four the poet gave the name "Philosophy which I realized". Yes, the philosophy realized by the poet is the eternal truth of the market of life. The veneration of mother earth is a common phenomenon in literature of all times. There are many references to this topic in the works of Abdulla Oripov. In the poet's poems about the Motherland, artistic images are expressed in such subtle verses that they contain neither artificial feelings nor lofty words. When a poet writes a poem about the Motherland, he does not confine himself to singing only about its beauty and acceptance. Perhaps his hard work truly describes his history and fate. The theme of nature occupies a large place in the poetry of the poet. In his poems, he writes about the seasons in nature, about day and night, about stars, mountains, springs, lawns. When you read his poems, you feel as if you hear the rustle of the water of the stream, and you see the leaves falling to the ground. The poet masterfully describes the harmony between nature and man. It should be noted that in the poems of Abdulla Oripov one can find not traditional means of expression, but often only allusions, adjectives, jokes inherent only to the poet. The phrases and sentences used by the poet are expressed in simple folk language, there is no silence or artificiality in them. These features are the reason why Abdulla Oripov's poems are popular among our people and loved by both young and old. It would not be an exaggeration to say that this is the greatest happiness of the poet, in whom almost every poem has become a song and lives in the hearts of people [4].

In general, the poetry of Abdulla Oripov is diverse both in subject matter and unique in artistic comprehension and image. After all, the poet takes readers into the mysterious world of artistic creativity, creating in all of them special symbols and images.

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